

against reciprocal of ionic radii of transition metal ions (Fig. 6) show that the ligands form weak complexes with Mg and stable complexes with Cu than with other bivalent transition metal ions.

Fig. 6.
a (x)
b (○)

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Studies of Formation Constants of Cinnamohydroxamic Acid Complexes with Lanthanum(III), Neodymium(III) and Samarium(III)

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THE flexibility of the coordination number of the rare earth ions¹ makes it interesting to study the nature of the rare earth-hydroxamate bond in the complexes with different types of simple and

substituted hydroxamic acids^{2,4}. The determination of stability constant values of some of the lanthanide-hydroxamate complexes, particularly those with NBPFA, was made previously². In the present communication, the formation constant values of three lanthanide ions La^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} with cinnamohydroxamic acid (CHA) in dioxane-water medium (3 : 1, v/v) are reported.

Experimental

The ligand cinnamohydroxamic acid (CHA) was prepared by the method described earlier³. The reagent was repeatedly recrystallised before use. The purity of the reagent was verified by m.p. (110-111°) determination and matching of ir spectra.

The perchlorates of the lanthanides used were prepared by digesting the corresponding oxides (Johnson Matthey, 99.9% pure) with perchloric acid and removing the excess acid by repeated evaporation. Finally, the perchlorates were dissolved in water and made up to definite volumes. Lanthanide ions were determined by oxalate precipitation and subsequent ignition to respective oxides⁴. Free perchloric acid present in the metal perchlorate solution were determined by running a known volume of the solution through a column of Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺-form) and titrating the liberated acid with a standard sodium hydroxide solution⁵ and subtracting the quantity of acid liberated M(III) ions.

Purified dioxane⁶ and double-distilled (CO₂-free) water were used for making solutions. All other chemicals were of A. R. grade.

Procedure: Experimental procedure consisted of titration of 40 ml dioxane-water (3 : 1, v/v) solutions containing $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ metal ion, $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ CHA and having a constant ionic strength (0.1 M) maintained by adding requisite amounts of sodium perchlorate with a standard solution of NaOH in an inert (nitrogen) atmosphere at $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The pH measurements were made with a Cambridge pH meter having a glass electrode (Universal type) and a calomel electrode connected to the cell by salt bridge. The acid dissociation constant of CHA was determined by a similar titration of the ligand in the absence of metal ion pH meter was calibrated using aqueous buffer solutions and the readings were converted to the stoichiometric hydrogen ion concentration incorporating correction for the use of mixed solvents⁷. The absence of polynuclear and hydroxo-complexes in the complexation equilibrium was checked by using two different concentrations of metal ions.

Results and Discussion

Successive formation constants K_1 , K_2 and K_3 were evaluated by analysing the formation function,

$$\sum_{n=0}^N (\bar{n}-n) [L^-]^n \beta_n \quad (1)$$

by the computational method of Rossotti and Rossotti⁶. Maximum $\bar{n}$ values obtained in the present experiments was 2.5 which also supports our assumption of 1 : 3 complex formation. Mean log K values are presented in Table 1. The overall stability constants log β_3 for the rare earth-cinnamohydroxamate complexes were not comparable to

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANT VALUES OF LANTHANIDE-CINNAMOHYDROXAMATE COMPLEXES IN DIOXANF-WATER SOLVENT

Temp. = $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$, $\mu = 0.1 M$
 $pK^HCHA = 6.93$

Metal ion	$1/r(A^{0-1})$	log K_1	log K_2	log K_3	log β_3
La ^{III}	0.942	4.04	3.92	2.98	10.91
Nd ^{III}	1.005	4.53	4.04	3.24	10.81
Sm ^{III}	1.037	4.84	4.26	3.41	12.51

those of NBPHA³ (in the same solvent mixture) or salicylhydroxamic acid⁹ (in acetone-water solvent). In fact the log β_3 values of the lanthanide-NBPHA (≈ 22) and salicylhydroxamate complexes (≈ 19) were much higher than those of CHA complexes (≈ 11). Solid complexes of La^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III} with CHA have been prepared and analysed. The composition of these complexes were found to be LnL₃·xH₂O (x=2 for La^{III} and 1 for Nd^{III} and Sm^{III}). The analytical data are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL DATA OF HYDRATED LANTHANIDE-CINNAMOHYDROXAMATE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found (Calcd.)		
		M	N	C
La(C ₉ H ₉ NO ₃) ₃ ·2H ₂ O	White	21.00 (21.01)	6.25 (6.35)	48.98 (49.02)
Nd(C ₉ H ₉ NO ₃) ₃ ·H ₂ O	Pale pink	21.70 (21.85)	6.45 (6.51)	50.00 (50.25)
Sm(C ₉ H ₉ NO ₃) ₃	White	22.95 (22.98)	6.40 (6.41)	49.55 (49.50)

The ir spectra of the solid complexes showed broad bands (above 3 000 cm⁻¹), which could be ascribed to the presence of either coordinated or lattice water¹⁰. The $\nu_{C=O}$ of CHA (1 665 cm⁻¹) has been found to shift to 1 640 cm⁻¹ in its sodium salt, whereas, for the lanthanide complexes a further shift towards lower frequencies (1 632 for La^{III}, 1 635 for Nd^{III} and 1 632 cm⁻¹ for Sm^{III} complexes) were observed. The strong ν_{ON} (at 1 350 cm⁻¹) and ν_{NO} (at 976 cm⁻¹) bands of the free ligand were shifted to 1 370 and 960 cm⁻¹, respectively in the complexes. Thus, the lanthanide ions were probably attached to two coordination sites (C=O and NHO⁻) of the cinnamohydroxamate ion.

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Rare Earths Complexes of some Amino Acids A Polarographic Study

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AMINO acids have been used as complexing reagents with various metal ions¹⁻³. Tewari and Shrivastava⁶ reported the stability constants of La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Y^{III} complexes with L-asparagine and L-glutamine by potentiometric technique. The present paper is continuation of our previous work⁷⁻⁹ and was undertaken with the view to determine the formation constants and thermodynamic parameters of Ce^{III} complexes with L-alanine, L-glutamine and L-asparagine on a dropping mercury electrode.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A. R. grade. The solution of L-alanine (Eastman & Kodak), L-glutamine (B. D. H., England) and L-asparagine (E. Merck) were prepared in double distilled water and their purity was checked by chromatographic method¹⁰. The metal solution was prepared by dissolving weighted quantity of CeCl₃·6H₂O (Fluka, A G.) in distilled water and was standardised with EDTA¹¹. The overall concentration of Ce^{III}, potassium chloride and gelatin in the test electrolytic solution was 1.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01%, respectively. The concentration of ligand was varied from 1.0 to 10.0 mM in each case. For the adjustment of ionic strength (μ) at 1.0 M, potassium chloride was used. Sodium hydroxide and hydro-